

Aryltin(IV)trifluoroacetates

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Aryltin(IV)trifluoroacetates, $R_nSn(OOCCF_3)_{4-n}$, where, $R = C_6H_5$, and $C_6H_5CH_2$, $n=2, 3$, have been prepared by metathetical reactions of the corresponding aryltin(IV) chlorides with silver trifluoroacetate in dichloromethane. Ir spectra indicate bridging trifluoroacetate groups in $\kappa_2SnOOCCF_3$ in solid state containing five coordinated tin, and bidentate trifluoroacetate groups in $R_2Sn(OOCCF_3)_2$. Mössbauer parameters support similar structures. 1H and ^{19}F nmr, and mass spectra are also discussed. $R_2Sn(OOCCF_3)_2$ form coordination complexes with nitrogen and oxygen donor ligands.

In continuation of our studies on organotin(IV)-trifluoroacetates¹⁻³, we now report the preparation and characterisation of hitherto unknown aryltin(IV)trifluoroacetates, $Ph_2Sn(OOCCF_3)_2$ (A), $Ph_3SnOOCCF_3$ (B), $(PhCH_2)_2Sn(OOCCF_3)_2$ (C) and $(PhCH_2)_3SnOOCCF_3$ (D), and the complexes of (A) and (C) with 2,2-dipyridyl (dipy), triphenylphosphine oxide (tppo) and 1,10-phenanthroline (phen).

Experimental

Dibenzyl- and tribenzyl-tin(IV) chlorides⁴ and silver trifluoroacetate⁵ were prepared by known methods. Diphenyl- and triphenyl-tin(IV) chlorides (Alfa Inorganics), 2,2'-dipyridyl (B.D.H.), triphenylphosphine oxide and 1,10-phenanthroline (E. Merck) were used as such. Trifluoroacetic acid (B.D.H.) was distilled in N_2 -atmosphere before use (b.p. $71.5^\circ/745$ torr).

In a typical preparation, stoichiometric amount of silver trifluoroacetate was added to a known weight (~ 3 mmol) of an aryltin(IV) chloride in dichloromethane. The contents were stirred at room temperature under N_2 -atmosphere for 3-4 h. The precipitated silver chloride was filtered off and the filtrate evaporated *in vacuo* to obtain the desired product.

Complexes with dipy, tppo and phen were prepared by adding dipy (1 : 1 mole ratio solution in CCl_4), tppo and phen (1 : 2 and 1 : 1 mole ratio solutions in benzene, respectively) to the solution of aryltin(IV)trifluoroacetate in carbon tetrachloride or benzene as required. The contents were stirred for about 3-4 h. The dipy-complexes are insoluble in CCl_4 and separate immediately on mixing the two solutions, the tppo-complexes were obtained by evaporating the solvent *in vacuo*. The phen-complexes were separated by adding dry petroleum ether (b.p. $40-60^\circ$). The products were filtered in N_2 -atmosphere, washed and dried *in vacuo*.

Results and Discussion

The trifluoroacetates⁶ (A-D) were prepared by metathetical reactions of the corresponding aryltin(IV) chlorides with silver trifluoroacetate in dichloromethane.

where, $R = C_6H_5$, $C_6H_5CH_2$; $n=2, 3$. These are colourless hygroscopic solids, soluble in polar and non-polar organic solvents. Their molecular weights in benzene (Table 1) indicate them to be monomeric. Molar conductance values in MeCN and $MeNO_2$ ($0.20-15.10 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) rule out their ionic nature. The complexes of (A) and (C) with dipy, tppo and phen, are white, hygroscopic solids. The analytical data are presented in Table 1.

Infrared spectra: The ir spectra (KBr/Nujol and 0.2 M solution in CCl_4) were recorded on a PE-621 spectrophotometer in the range $4000-200 cm^{-1}$. In view of the low symmetry of the trifluoroacetate group, different types of its coordination cannot be distinguished on the basis of a number of ir/Raman-active bands⁷. Attempts have been made to relate the values of asymmetric and symmetric C-O stretching frequencies and their separation to the mode of trifluoroacetate coordination⁸⁻¹⁰. The position of $\nu_{asym} CO_2$ has been utilised in deciding the bonding mode¹¹ of trifluoroacetate groups in (A-D). The $\nu_{asym} COO$ in (A-D) appear at; solid (solution): (A) 1660s (1660s); (B) 1652s br (1710s); (C) 1662s (1660s); (D) 1653s (1712s) cm^{-1} . Positions of $\nu_{asym} COO$ in (A) and (C) are consistent with the bidentate trifluoroacetate groups¹². Solid and solution spectra of these compounds show no change. Triorganotin(IV)carboxylates in solid state have trigonal bipyramidal structures having five-coordinated tin. The crystal structure¹³ of $Me_3SnOOCCF_3$ indicates its polymeric nature with bridging COO groups¹⁴, $\nu_{asym} COO$, 1652 (1720) cm^{-1} .

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF ARYLtin(IV)TRIFLUOROACETATE AND THEIR COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					M.p. °C	Mol. wt. Found/ Calcd.
	Sn	F	O	H	N		
Ph ₂ Sn(OOCCF ₃) ₂ (A)	28.6 (28.8)	22.7 (22.8)	28.0 (28.5)	1.98 (2.00)	—	142.1	510 (498.7)
Ph ₂ SnOOCCF ₃ (B)	25.4 (25.6)	19.2 (19.3)	51.7 (51.8)	8.20 (8.24)	—	121.1	484 (462.7)
(PhOH) ₂ Sn(OOCCF ₃) ₂ (C)	22.4 (22.5)	21.6 (21.6)	40.9 (41.0)	2.60 (2.65)	—	72.7	540 (526.7)
(PhCH ₂) ₂ SnOOCCF ₃ (D)†	23.4 (23.5)	11.2 (11.8)	54.0 (54.6)	4.12 (4.16)	—	75.8	515 (504.7)
(A).dipy	17.9 (18.1)	17.3 (17.4)	47.5 (47.6)	2.70 (2.75)	4.22 (4.27)	198.2	—
(C).dipy	17.2 (17.4)	16.6 (16.7)	49.1 (49.2)	8.20 (8.22)	4.02 (4.10)	130.1	—
(A).Stppo	11.2 (11.8)	10.6 (10.8)	59.0 (59.2)	8.75 (8.79)	—	125.1	—
(C).Stppo	10.7 (10.9)	10.2 (10.5)	59.4 (59.8)	8.98 (4.06)	—	120.1	—
(A).phen	17.2 (17.5)	18.7 (18.8)	49.4 (49.5)	2.61 (2.65)	4.10 (4.12)	>220	—
(C).phen	16.7 (16.8)	16.0 (16.1)	50.8 (50.9)	8.10 (8.11)	8.90 (8.96)	125-126	—

* Sn was determined as SnO₂, F (Ref. 6), and O and H microanalytically.

The ν_{asym} COO frequencies in (B) and (D) are comparable with those in Me₂SnOOCCF₃. A comparison of the carbonyl frequencies in the solid and solution spectra of (B) and (D) shows the expected shift from the monomeric ester form in solution to the polymeric form with bridging COO groups in solid. Medium to strong bands at 1150-1210 cm⁻¹ are attributed to ν_{CF_3} , whereas the bands appearing around 790, 440 and 290 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to δ_{OCO} , $\nu_{\text{Sn-C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Sn-O}}$, respectively. These band positions show no change in solid or solution.

No significant changes are observed in the spectra of (A) and (C) on complexation with the ligands, except for the positions of the asymmetric carbonyl stretching frequencies. In complexes, ν_{asym} COO in 1710-1720 cm⁻¹ region strongly suggests unidentate coordination of the trifluoroacetato groups¹⁰. Expected shifts in the ligand vibrations have been observed on complexation¹⁰⁻¹².

Mössbauer spectra : The Mössbauer parameters of (A-D) are : (δ (A) 1.37, (B) 1.47, (C) 1.57 and (D) 1.55 ; ΔE_q (A) 2.58, (B) 4.04, (C) 4.20 and (D) 3.64 mm s⁻¹). Quadrupole splitting values play an important rôle in deciding about the relative positions in dialkyl/aryltin(IV) compounds¹³. For their *trans*-arrangements ΔE_q is ~ 4 mm s⁻¹, whereas for *cis*-arrangements the value is half. Benzyl groups in dibenzyltin(IV) trifluoroacetate are in *trans*-position. Phenyl groups in diphenyltin(IV)trifluoroacetate are *cis* as revealed from its ΔE_q value. Most of the diphenyltin(IV) compounds are known to be *cis*^{13,14}. The δ and ΔE_q values for (B) and (D) are comparable to those reported for other pentacoordinated R₂SnX systems^{14,15}; as for four-coordinated systems, the ΔE_q is 2.3 mm s⁻¹.

Nmr spectra : The room temperature ¹⁹F nmr spectra (Varian EM-390) of CCl₄ and CH₂Cl₂ solutions of compounds (A-D) exhibit a single peak [(A) 74.8, (B) 74.9, (C) 75.7 and (D) 75.5 ppm] upfield with respect to CCl₃F. The chemical shifts are independent of the solvent used. The presence of a single peak indicates free rotation of the CF₃ moiety about C-C bond. A small spread of chemical shifts in organotin(IV) trifluoroacetates^{1,16} restricts the utility of ¹⁹F nmr data for deciding the nature of coordination of trifluoroacetate groups.

The magnitude of the chemical shifts of various protons in pmr spectra of the complexes [(A) δ_o 7.75, $\delta_{m,p}$ 7.62 ; (B) δ_o 7.68, $\delta_{m,p}$ 7.55 ; (C) δ_{CH} 3.0, δ_{arom} 7.4 ; (D) δ_{CH} 2.6, δ_{arom} 7.5 ppm, where *o*=ortho, *m*=meta, *p*=para] are comparable to the reported values for similar types of compounds¹⁷.

Mass spectra : In the mass spectra of (A-D), only ¹¹⁸Sn peaks have been assigned. The base peak is mainly a tri coordinated tin-containing ion. The common features are high stability of SnR₃⁺ ion and low abundance of the parent ions. Similar results have been reported for other organotin(IV) compounds^{18,19}.

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